

Figure 3. Extended Framework for ECM Research (based on Tyrväinen et al., 2006; vom Brocke et al., 2011c)

IV. DISCUSSIONS

A variety of academic sources were searched for ECM literature to gain a comprehensive, in-depth insight into the current state of the research field. To ensure a multifaceted spectrum of authors and opinions, the screening of the literature was mild. In total, 68 articles were identified as relevant and reviewed. As a broad range of different scientific articles was chosen, the reviewed literature is diverse: in length, focus, and in its research contribution. Although some papers lack scientific background, several made an important contribution to IS research. However, ECM as a research topic has not yet reached the highest academic outlets and conferences are the main source of ECM literature. This review supports prior findings that indicate that ECM research is still in an immature state (vom Brocke, Derungs, Herbst, Novotny, Simons, 2011b, p. 10) and includes a small body of literature (Grahlmann et al., 2011, p. 2).

Two limitations have been identified for this research: Since ECM research is still relatively young, it lacks consistent and well-accepted definitions (vom Brocke et al., 2011c, p. 493). ECM as a concept and research field is still evolving, therefore definitions are not final. Accordingly, the definitions in this paper are labeled as working definitions and do not claim to be final. Further, there is no guarantee that some relevant articles were not found or considered, even though the search process was exhaustive. There were no boundaries about the time period. However, there is a thematic restriction to the ECM domain. Due to this restriction, EDM articles that did not explicitly address ECM were excluded. Important contributions to the EDM domain were made by Sprague, Päiväranta, Tyrväinen, Karjalainen/Honkaranta, and Salminen to name a few. Because EDM is one of the closest ancestors of ECM (Päiväranta and Munkvold, 2005), researchers who are conducting ECM research should be aware of it.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This ECM research writing combines and sums up earlier exploration and coordinates the discoveries in a concept centric way. From a neutral point of view, 68 articles were evaluated and categorized. A description of the ECM domain was done; The main ideas and topics were derived. Working definitions were included in the adoption, refinement, and explanation of an established framework for ECM research. Further, ramifications for exploration and practice were drawn.

ECM research is still in its infancy in the current state. The assortment of writing of this arising research field is little, yet consistently developing. More specific research needs to be done: There is little requirement for specialized approaches, but instead for more examination centering a nitty gritty reference model, ECM processes, the endeavor viewpoint, and clients of ECMS. In general, there needs to be more quantitative work done. Based on this paper, further in-depth discussions and a more specific research plan can be developed.

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